

REVIEW OF LITERATURE DEDICATED TO THE IMPORTANT DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES OF PATHOLOGIES OF SALIVARY GLANDS OF VARIOUS ETIOLOGIES.

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Relevance. Differential diagnosis of conditions characterized by the general symptom of decreased salivation (hyposalivation) is a difficult task, especially considering the variety of causes affecting the processes of regulation of salivation. Typically, damage to the salivary glands is secondary and occurs against the background of diseases of the internal organs, while early symptoms of damage to the salivary glands often go unnoticed for a long time. Disturbances in the functioning of the salivary glands are often associated with endocrine disorders. The use of standard clinical examination methods, such as anamnesis, visual examination, palpation and laboratory tests, is a simple and effective diagnostic method that allows not only to identify the pathological process, but also to identify concomitant diseases.

Target- based on a detailed study of specialized sources, identify the most effective and accessible approaches to diagnosing patients with various pathologies of the salivary glands.

Materials and methods of research. A review of scientific literature published over the past five years was carried out.

Hence, determination of lysozyme flow rate by analyzing a single saliva sample using a calculation method cannot be considered a reliable indicator of the actual flow rate. To eliminate inaccuracies in salivary lysozyme concentration measurements caused by rapid changes in the secretion of this enzyme, it is recommended to collect three saliva samples every 10 minutes with a 30-minute break between the start of each collection. Research shows that when analyzing oral resistance factors, most scientists focus on salivary lysozyme levels, but concentrations of beta-lysine and secretory immunoglobulin A (sIgA) should also be examined to further understand this issue.

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